

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

This article describes the methodology of teaching English to children of preschool and primary school age, which is the main link to continuous education. Also, several instructions are given regarding interactive methods, requirements for teachers, and improvement of lesson efficiency. More results can be achieved by conducting lessons that take into account the interests of each child. It is appropriate to use intellectual games, modern technologies, and new methods during the lesson.

Key words: interactive, intellectual, talent, method, technology, character, multimedia, game

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Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in research in English, which is recognized as the language of professional communication in various fields of activity. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of the teacher is to increase the enthusiasm for learning English. Every teacher tries to find the best way to solve the problem. In order to familiarize students with the culture of the country of the studied language, the use of traditional methods and means of influencing them is being considered, and new technologies are being introduced, one of which is game technology.

Work using visual aids, posters, songs, and books. Children's thinking remains abstract, and the process of obtaining new knowledge is always focused on emotions for primary school kids in rural settings. As a result, kindergarten English teachers make full use of materials available to kids, flashcards, and other teaching aids when teaching using simple approaches. When teaching words like "banana" and "apple," teachers can teach new color words at the same time by displaying fruits like bananas and apples. Children learn to organize learning activities in their foreign language by using classroom items. At the same time, the approach of the teachers has a significant impact on the usage of resources during instruction. For example, while teaching related terms, you show the child the object and urge him to say it first, then the pupils utter the words and repeat the new phrase using the pictures on the cards to reinforce the word they have pronounced. Teachers can determine the content of the text in the teaching of words, and to grab the students' attention, the educator can draw their picture on the board by speaking the words with them. So now, the tutor needs to know how to draw. This makes things easier. Teaching helps students learn and also helps them remember what they've learned. To proceed or accomplish something to help students see their improvement in learning

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English, it's important to have a good plan. The way we do things in school This is the best way to encourage kids to want to learn. Today, children who are of kindergarten age can learn new things easily and quickly. Teaching programs have been increased as needed.

Making a classroom where things can change easily is often more important than how we teach. In the class, the teacher and all the children sang a fun English song and danced a little at the start of the lesson. This will help them work out, have more energy, and learn the song lyrics faster. The English environment makes it easy to learn and creates a good atmosphere for learning. Children have a hard time controlling themselves and staying focused for a long time. So, the teacher should give the kids songs, poems, or cartoons they enjoy to help them learn the language. When learning outside dialect, children don't get the words in cartoons but attempt to get the words they utilize through the activities of cartoon characters. That's a fun and compelling way for children to memorize language.

Conclusion

Nowadays, all kindergartens are equipped with mixed-media hardware. Children learn English through melodies, lyrics, stories, and recordings. It turns boring dialect lessons into an energizing day-to-day diversion. The kindergarten has around 10 children per bunch, and instructors regularly utilize instructive strategies based on each child's brain research. This requires the teacher to be not only a teacher but also a craftsman, a performer, a remote dialect instructor, and a great mother analyst.

Through signals and facial expressions: When the educator talks something to the children or gives an arrangement, for illustration, when utilizing signals, the child will get these words. Motion is the foremost critical teaching strategy in English. Chinese kindergarten makes a difference when children effectively discover the Chinese title for something in English. Nearly each teacher knows that creature motions are the most straightforward way within the planning handle his appearance in a marginally bowed position. For children with an imitative nature, this will exceptionally curiously and promptly make them say the title of the creature spoken to, which is able to energize you to keep in mind the recently learned words. In China, one-child families are the lion's share. In this manner, children of single-child families have an awfully manly character. At this point, we ought to say that of the teacher. It'll not be simple to discover a way into the hearts of children with such a character. The teacher ought to have a kind eye and a delicate grin; this will stir the adoration for the extraordinary teacher in children.

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